

IMPACT OF LIQUIDITY ON PROFITABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Management of liquidity and profitability has become a crucial issue in today's cutthroat competition in business. Apparently, liquidity and profitability goals conflict in most of the decisions, which the finance manager makes. In this direction, the present study analyzed the financial performance of BHEL ltd. by establishing the relationship between liquidity and profitability with Multiple Regression Model for the period from 2007 to 2016. The calculated Current ratios and Super Quick Ratios are below the standard norm in the study period. Further, the study also observed that the ROI was down ward trend. The coefficients of Quick Ratio, Super Quick Ratio, and Debt Equity Ratio are negative and insignificant, shows negative effect of these ratios on Return of Investment. The coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio is negative and statistically significant at 10 percent probability level. The study reveals that impact of liquidity on profitability was negative.

INTRODUCTION

Profitability and liquidity are the most prominent issues that management of each organization. Liquidity refers to the ability of a firm to meet its short-term obligations. Liquidity plays a crucial role in the successful functioning of a business firm. A study of liquidity is of major importance to both the internal and external analysis because of its close relationship with day-to-day operations of a business. A weak liquidity position poses a threat to the solvency as well as profitability of a firm and makes it unsafe and unsound.

Profitability is measure of the amount by which a firm's revenues exceeds its relevant expenses. Potential investors are interested in dividends and appreciation in market price of stock, so they pay more attention on the profitability ratios. Managers on the other hand are interested in measuring the operating performance in terms of profitability. Hence, a low profit margin would suggest ineffective management and investors would be hesitant to invest in the company. The liquidity and profitability goals are contradictory to each other in most decisions, which the finance manager takes. For example, the firm by following a lenient credit policy may be in a position to increase its sales, but its liquidity may tend to worse. In addition to this, referring to the risk return theory there is a direct relationship between risk and return. Thus, firm with high liquidity may have low risk and then low profitability. Conversely, firm that has low liquidity may face high-risk results to higher return. Consequently, a firm is required to maintain a balance between liquidity and profitability in its day-to-day operations.

In fact, liquidity is a prerequisite for the very survival of a business firm. Liquidity verses profitability management has thus, become a basic and broad aspect of judging the performance of a corporate entity. It is, therefore, essential to maintain an adequate degree of liquidity for smooth running of the business operations. The liquidity should be neither excessive nor adequate. Excessive liquidity indicates accumulation of idle funds, which do not earn any profit for the firm, and inadequate liquidity does not only adversely affect the credit.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Padachi (2006) in his study found that high investment in inventories and receivables is associated with lower profitability. Christopher and Kamalavalli (2009) signify that working capital component negatively influence profitability. Lazard's and Tryfonidis (2006) study showed that there is a statistical significance between profitability, measured through gross operating profit, and the cash conversion cycle. Chakraborty (2008) evaluated the relationship between working capital and profitability of Indian pharmaceutical companies. Dong and Su (2010) examined the relationship between profitability, the cash conversion cycle and its component for listed firms in Vietnam

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stock market for period (2006-2008) and they resulted that there is strong negative relationship between cash conversion cycle and the profitability.

Velnampy and Nimalathasan (2010) using sample of Bank of Ceylon and Commercial Bank of Ceylon ltd in Sri Lanka, found that there is a positive relationship between firm size and profitability in Commercial Bank of Ceylon ltd, but there is no relationship between firm size and profitability in Bank of Ceylon. Qasim Saleem, Ramiz Ur Rehman (2011) made a research on Impacts of liquidity ratios on profitability of selected enterprises in Pakistan with the sample of 26 oil and gas companies listed under the Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE). Findings reveal that there is a significant impact of only liquid ratio on ROA while insignificant on ROE and ROI; the results also show that ROE is no significant effected by three ratios current ratio, quick ratio and liquid ratio. Bhunia, et. al. (2011) investigated the liquidity management efficiency and liquidity profitability relationship. The data utilized was extracted from the income statements, balance sheets, and cash flow statements of sampled firms from the India Stock Exchange and CMEI data base. The purposive sample design method was applied in their analysis. Preferred sample of private sector steel companies from 1997-2006 were utilized in the analysis. Results showed that correlation and regression results are positively significant and associated to the firm profitability.

Ajanthan (2013) investigated the relationship between liquidity and profitability of trading companies in Sri Lanka over a period of past 5 years from 2008 to 2012. The study reveals that there is a significant relationship exists between liquidity and profitability among the listed trading companies in Sri Lanka. Makori and Jagongo (2013) study indicated that current ratio, advantage with sales progress as well as size ensure significant belongings on the profitability of firms. Sandhar and Janglani (2013) empirically inspected the relationship between liquidity and profitability. The researchers exposed current ratio and liquid ratio is negatively related with ROI & ROA. Warred (2015) in his research paper sets out to investigate the impact of the liquidity on fifteen Jordanian listed Banks (ASE) profitability through Return on assets on the banking sector of Jordan-Amman from 2005- 2011 through simple regressions. The study reveals that there is a significant impact of quick ratio on return on asset of Jordanian banks

STUDY OBJECTIVE

Management of liquidity and profitability has become a crucial issue in today’s cutthroat competition in business. Liquidity and profitability are very closely related. Apparently, liquidity and profitability goals conflict in most of the decisions, which the finance manager makes. In this direction, the present study attempted to examine the impact of liquidity on profitability of Bharat Heavy Electronics Limited (BHEL) for the period of 10 years through liquidity ratios.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Source of Data: The data for this study have extracted from the Annual Report of Bharat Heavy Electronics Limited (BHEL) from CMIE database for the period of 10 years i.e. from 2006 to 2016.

Tools of Analysis: In this section, an attempt has been made to examine composite impact of liquidity indicators on profitability of Bharat Heavy Electronics Limited (BHEL) through the following Multiple Regression Model suggested by Rafuse (1996), Singh (2008) and Bhunia (2010) by using SPSS-17 version.

ROI = f (CR, QR, SQR, DER, ICR, ITR, DTR, CTR)

ROI = β₀ + β₁ CR + β₂ QR + β₃ SQR + β₄ DER + β₅ ICR + β₆ ITR + β₇ DTR + β₈ CTR + E

Where,

- CR = Current Ratio = Current Assets/ Current Liabilities
- QR =Quick Ratio = Liquid Assets/ Current Liabilities
- SQR =Super Quick Ratio = (Cash + Marketable Securities)/Current Liabilities
- DER =Debt-to-Equity Ratio = Total liabilities/Shareholders Equity
- ICR =Interest Coverage Ratio = EBIT/Interest Expense
- ITR =Inventory Turnover Ratio = Cost of Goods Sold/Average Stock
- DTR =Debtors Turnover Ratio = Net Credit Sales/Average trade Debtors

ROI = Return on Investment = Net profit after Tax and Interest/Dividend declare

E is the error term and β_0 is intercept of linear function

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7$ and β_8 are the linear parameters of the ROI

DATA ANALYSIS

The calculated liquidity ratios of BHEL Ltd were presented in Table-1 along with the profitability ratio ROI. The calculated CR and SQR are less than standard norm in the study period. The calculated QR was greater than standard norm from 2007 to 2016. The DTR was very low in the study period. The calculated ICR, ITR and DTR are fluctuating in the study period. The ROI of the firm was continuously decreasing from 49.51 to 10.90 in the study period 2006 to 2016, indicates the financial performance of the firm is in downward trend and unsatisfactory in the study period.

Table-1: Liquidity Ratios of BHEL

Year	CR	QR	SQR	DER	ICR	ITR	DTR	ROI
2006-07	1.34	0.91	0.17	0.04	26.76	1.66	3.43	49.51
2007-08	1.33	0.97	0.23	0.03	72.47	2.56	3.98	41.96
2008-09	1.44	1.04	0.13	0.01	60.35	1.69	4.67	42.44
2009-10	1.51	1.17	0.17	0.01	29.71	1.73	4.09	42.41
2010-11	1.64	1.25	0.26	0.02	45.98	1.61	2.88	37.67
2011-12	1.73	1.35	0.21	0.01	76.18	1.62	2.17	31.68
2012-13	1.68	1.16	0.11	0.04	71.92	1.23	2.12	29.25
2013-14	1.62	1.21	0.10	0.03	90.04	1.48	2.34	19.41
2014-15	1.54	1.24	0.11	0.05	87.18	1.51	2.16	18.80
2015-16	1.54	1.25	0.73	0.03	57.98	1.42	2.06	10.90

Sources: Annual Reports of BHEL

Regression Analysis

The estimated regression coefficients and other statistics of ROI function were presented in Table-2

Table-2: Estimated Regression Coefficients and other Statistics

Particulars	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Con	β_0	50.67	118.06		0.43	0.71
CR	β_1	36.84	56.55	0.40	0.65	0.58
QR	β_2	-54.07	35.12	-0.60	-1.54	0.26
SQR	β_3	-28.40	16.75	-0.42	-1.70	0.23
DER	β_4	-211.28	375.35	-0.24	-0.56	0.63
ICR	β_5	-0.34	0.12	-0.59**	-2.87	0.10
ITR	β_6	14.86	8.62	0.41	1.72	0.23
DTR	β_7	-1.43	7.69	-0.11	-0.19	0.87
R ² = 0.96*		F = 6.72*		S.E. = 5.42		

Note: *Indicates Significant at 5 per cent Probability level.

**Indicates Significant at 10 per cent Probability level.

Sources: Authors Compilation

Before analyzing the table-2, we should examine the multi-collinearity in Correlation Matrix at Table-3 and found the absence of multi-collinearity. The estimated R² value of the model is 0.96. Based on F test, it is significant at 5 per cent probability level, indicating 96 percent variation is explained between the independent variables

(components of liquidity) and the dependent variable (ROI). Hence, the estimated relationship is true and the fit is good.

Table-3: Correlation Matrix

Ratios	DTR	SQR	DER	ICR	ITR	QR	CR
DTR	1.000						
SQR	.694	1.000					
DER	.891	.595	1.000				
ICR	.120	.255	-.147	1.000			
ITR	.153	.169	.378	-.424	1.000		
QR	.166	-.294	.211	-.216	-.059	1.000	
CR	.720	.724	.726	-.053	.495	-.411	1.000

Note: Dependent Variable: ROI

Sources: Authors Compilation

From the table-2, we observed that the coefficients of Current Ratio (0.40) and Interest Turnover Ratio (0.41) are positive. The coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio (-0.59) is negative and statistically significant at 10 percent probability level indicates the significance of this ratio on ROI of BHEL. The coefficients of Quick Ratio (-0.60), Super Quick Ratio (-0.42), Debt Equity Ratio (-0.24) are negative and insignificant, shows negative effect of these ratios on Return of Investment of BHEL in the study period 2006-2016

CONCLUSIONS

Management of liquidity and profitability has become a crucial issue in today's cutthroat competition in business. Liquidity and profitability are very closely related. If the firm decreases its liquidity, the profitability may be high. Apparently, liquidity and profitability goals conflict in most of the decisions, which the finance manager makes. In this direction, the present study analyzed the financial performance of BHEL Ltd. by establishing the relationship between liquidity and profitability with Multiple Regression Model for the period from 2007 to 2016. The calculated Current ratios and Super Quick Ratios are below the standard norm in the study period. Further, the study also observed that the ROI was down ward trend from 49.15 to 10.90. The coefficients of Quick Ratio (-0.60), Super Quick Ratio (-0.42), Debt Equity Ratio (-0.24) are negative and insignificant, shows negative effect of these ratios on Return of Investment of BHEL. The coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio (-0.59) is negative and statistically significant at 10 percent probability level, indicates the significance of this ratio on ROI. The study reveals that impact of liquidity on profitability was negative.

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LAND ALIENATION AND TRIBAL DISPLACEMENT: A STUDY ON TRIBAL COMMUNITY IN LALGARH OF WEST BENGAL

Dr. Partha Sarathi Bhattacharjee³

PRELUDE

India is a secular country where people from different caste and creeds are living according to their choice. After independence, though India has shown remarkable progress in science and technology but this development has failed to change the life style and living fashion to certain segments of our population. The tribal people (8%) of total population are peace lover and they live in forests or in the wasteland, their process of life also depends upon the productivity from natural resources. They are recognized as tribal accordingly their rights are protected in our constitution. Though the majority of our population in the country is progressing and their life style has been changed, the condition of the tribals remains unchanged. Though government initiated adequate steps to the tribal development later, it took U-turn because of changes in policies for modern development and industrialization process. The scarcity of lands due to mass population has left no other option with the government other than to use the instrument for encroachment of land and using natural resources for the development that lead to the tribal unrest. Lalgarh in West Bengal is not exception to witness all these episodes. It is located in Binpur I Subdivision West Midnapore District in West Bengal. 57% of total population are scheduled tribes and they lived in nature in symbiotic relation with ecology and environment and their livelihood security depends upon the production from forests, ponds etc. Deforestation about 4500 acres of land in Salboni for the industrialization process in the recent times which was felt by these people are insecure for their survival resulted in protests and violence in Lalgarh.

Issues: The recent development model which has been adopted by the state government in Lalgarh where more than 57% of total population are tribal, embedding the new economic policies of liberalization, privatization and globalization in using natural resources, particularly lands, forests and rivers is a serious question for leading their natural life thereby survival. The state government invited industrialist like Jindal and Santosa (Indonesia) for making Special Economic Zone (SEZ) deforesting around 4500 acres of lands and encroached about 500 acres of tribal lands on absence of original landowners, using an instrument, which is a destruction to the environment and has a devastating impact on their health.

The last resources for their survival have been taken away in the name of development project where these people have no role to play; they will remain unemployed due to lack of requisite skills for the modern industries pushed them to the brink of hunger and acute malnutrition. The majority of the people now divested and displaced from their lands. According to **Marx** in a capitalist society an alienated many lives in an alienated nature, he performs estranged labour, and the product of his labour becomes alien to him. **Philip (1991)** discussed the land alienation of tribals and its impact on their socio-economic structures starting from the agrarian changes. **The Rio de Jenerio (1992)** declaration on environment and development by the UN conference proclaims that state should regularize and duly support indigenous people's identity, cultures, interest and enable their participation in the achievement of sustainable development. **Roy (1995)** suggests that the impact of displacement and other form of deprivation on subaltern women and men, one has to begin by looking at the traditional social structure of subaltern groups. **Guha (1996)** views that patta land is alienated from its owner, its non-owning dependents are impoverished and pushed further down the socio economic ladder. **International Labour Organisation (2002)** suggested that government must consult with indigenous and tribal people within their country on development projects and other activities affecting them.

OBJECTIVES

- To determine the rift of stakeholders and people of Lalgarh in the process of Industrialization.
- To assess the role of State Government.

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- To examine the livelihood securities of tribal people
- To assess the role played by the tribal community for protecting the natural resources in the way of violation
- To examine the impact of the violence in the affected areas.

METHODOLOGY

Non-participant observation methods were applied for collecting data in the tribal community in Lalgarh area to ascertain their livelihood condition. Interview guide and a focus group discussion taking 10 people in a group was a useful method to collect the data. Secondary data like Government report, newspaper and media reports are also used in this study.

FINDINGS

The underlying hope that the development would finally reach the poor tribals was getting belied day- by- day. There was a wide lag between the needs of the tribals in Lalgarh and states own vision of development, which was often dictated by the ruling elites and corporate.

All round development of the tribals is the need of the hour.

The state, which had the responsibility for providing protection, itself, became an interested party.

This movements of tribal people against their forced displacement and the corporate grab of their resources is being sought to be violently crushed by the use of police and security forces and state and corporate funded and armed militias.

Operation Green Hunt in which a huge number of paramilitary forces are being used mostly on the tribals has accentuated the state violence.

The militarization of the state has reached a level where schools are occupied by security forces.

The police and administrations are also victimizing the local peace loving people other than tribals.

This has led to a total alienation of the people from the state as well as their loss of faith in the government and the security forces resulted in supports from Maoists.

SUGGESTIONS

Considering the above scenario, the following suggestions may be incorporated in policy formulation:

The path of violation never bring success that message must be communicated to tribal people so that they can understand the message properly with the view to get rid of violent path and to come forward to discuss all their issues in the negotiable table with Govt. authority.

All demands may be scrutinized at an appropriate level in the Government organization. An open mind discussions may be highly solicited.

The modality for implementations of the system need to be discussed in presence of all the affected population and channel of supervising the work progress may be strengthened in such a way so that tasks may be completed without any further delay and hindrance.

However, Government of Bengal has done much to improve the quality of life of adivasis offering various schemes but much need to be done. The voice of grass route people should be listened carefully to solve the present issues.

Health and Education is a prime important now-a-days. Breaking down these systems arrest the development of the society and paralyzed the complete systems that need to be attended as an emergency manner.

Public-private sector are the main composition in the present world that helps to create more jobs in both public and private sectors with the speedy implementation of the systematic method.

Human Rights Commission must be strong enough to protect the rights of tribal in that region where they are subjected to harass by either the local authorities or common people.

The deprivation of tribal groups to benefit a Private company could shake the faith of tribal people in the loss of land, which may have serious consequences for the security, and wellbeing of the people of entire country

CONCLUSION

The reality is that all these struggles represented the genuine interests and aspiration of the lower level people those are oppressed and suppressed by the capitalist / industrialist. Here in Lalgarh the conditions of tribals are no exception. These indigenous people have a unique cultural identity. However, they are getting step motherly treatment from the government without recognizing their indigenous status, neglected them in terms of development and denied their rights and justice. Corruptions, negligence and poor capacity to solve their issues among local politicians and administrators impeded development in the region. Police atrocities on tribal in this region continue to be unabated. Therefore, they feel most vulnerable and have lost their hope in the democracy thereby adoption of the path of violence. Gun battle against these people may not be appropriate to address their genuine issues. The government must understand the ground realities so that appropriate mechanism can be adopted to solve their problems once for all.

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THE ROLE OF HUMAN SENSES IN CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF A HIGH INVOLVEMENT PRODUCT CATEGORY: THE CASE OF BRANDED APPAREL

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ABSTRACT

Branded apparels and related products are aspirational buys for the consumer. This exploratory study attempts to understand the role of the human senses in determining consumer buying behaviour in the specific context of apparel purchase. Empirical studies on sensory experiences are a relatively unexplored area of research in clothing and apparel buying behaviour among differently abled consumers. The senses that aid the process of product purchase such as visual, auditory and kinesthetic are the independent variables studied in this research paper. To enable a finer evaluation of buying behaviour of consumers in an apparel buying setting constructs from neuro-marketing and buyology are analysed: price, sales, promotion, advertising, impulse buying, design and trend, and are as the dependent variables studied in this research paper. The exploratory research study presents an empirical treatment of data collected from 230 respondents in the geographical area of Bengaluru. Random sampling was used as the technique for data collection while statistical tools for data analysis used KMO, communality test, reliability, Chi square, correlation and regression analysis.

KEYWORDS

Human Senses, Impact, Selection and Buying Behaviour, Visual, Auditory, Kinaesthetic, Correlation, Regression etc.

INTRODUCTION

Apparels are aspirational products and tend to offer strong brand personalization benefits to the user. The consumers' choices depend progressively and significantly on subjective elements such as emotions, pictures, impressions and requests of the items. Apparels, as product offerings, play a role in developing a consumer's attitude while highlighting personality characteristics of a consumer. The granularity of the evoked set of factors that drive purchase decision of a consumer acquire complex dimensions when sensory variables are extended to a differently-abled consumer. The absence of a good appearance can lead to challenges associated with self-image. This can be more sensitive in the case of differently abled people. These boundaries show how the function of attire, material and building configuration groups with information of tangible issues alternate lend themselves to tactile experience.

The different dimensions that could be considered on the selection and buying behaviour of consumers considering apparel are human senses, price, design and trends, impulse buying and sales and promotion. The three senses considered here are visual, auditory and kinaesthetic senses. Since the other two senses which are taste and smell, do not play a role in the selection of apparel and does not affect the buying behaviour of consumers are not considered in this study.

Visual senses play a key role in affect the self-image of the consumer and actions that trigger arousal to buy apparel. It also depends on how the individual looks at the apparel and how the apparel appears to the eye of the individual. The eye level could be affected by how the clothes are displayed, the mannequins display, the design and many others factors. The visual effects could be in 2D or 3D effects. The display could be through a picture or in real, which relates to other human senses that could help in apparel selection. The visual reactions can excite neural impulses, which could impact on neuro framework on the individual and facilitate appropriate decision making. Auditory sense, stirs a considerable measure of emotions amid the determination and the path toward purchasing an

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apparel product. Tuning into individuals about most recent patterns and form, impact people in determination and purchasing of apparels and texture. Auditory factors, as similar to word of mouth, in shopping play a major role in the selection of apparel. Kinaesthetic sense allows for the selection of apparel as also the feeling of the fabric and the texture.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Dash, Mihir; Akshaya (2014) explores visual impact on apparel purchase and examines the role of store layout, mannequin display, promotional advertisement, product display and so on in understanding the buying behaviour of consumers.

Wu, Juanjuan; WonJu, Hae; Kim, Jieun; Damminga, Cara; Kim, HyeYoung (2012) e. investigates the role of colour, visual texture and style effect factors in the purchase of products as also the interest of consumers, pleasure perception and purchase behaviour. This exploratory study explored the impact of style, colour and visual appeal among consumers accessing virtual stores.

Wang, Ying; Chen, Yan; Zhi-ge, Chen (2006) explores consumers' perception (sensory engineering) influence on the senses, feelings and design perception. The study concluded that the senses could be related to the purchase behaviour of clothing.

Osmud Rahman (2003) depicts how visual and file input have an effect on purchase intention of denim apparel. Both sensory and cognitive responses were investigated using quantitative methods. The conclusions drawn from the research indicated that the respondents were specific to the fabric feel, fitting, physical durability and the visual aspects of the product in denim purchase evaluation.

Subhani, Muhammad Imtiaz; Hasan, Syed Akif; Osman, Amber (2011) study how apparels have an impact on the mood of consumers. The effect could be based on the feel, personality and other demographic factors. The paper also depicts how the mood of the individual has an effect on the dressing behaviour of the individual. There could be a number of other factors that could affect the dressing behaviour of an individual. The factors such as emotions, quality of the fabric, situations, print, design, colour, education of a person etc., could be useful in identifying an individual.

Song, Kun; Fiore, Ann Marie; Park, Jihye (2006) explored how the online shopping experience influenced consumers in the selection and buying behaviour of apparel. The online experience helps in bringing about a different perception as virtual shopping experience is not taken into account and this could be a negative aspect about online shopping. Telepresence experience and the fantasy could influence shopping experience.

Methods: A dress displayed at a retail establishment or a promotion may draw thought, and also energize diverse class responses. Regardless, if the watcher hates the presence of a dress, he or she may not wish to take a glance at the thing further, for instance, by feeling the texture or endeavouring the piece of attire on. Along these lines, it is obvious that just by advertisements or other such means the customer needs can't be fulfilled. Hence, there is a need to focus the impact on how the human senses influence the determination of attire. The empirical study is specific to the geographical region of Bangalore. This particular study depicts how the conceptual factors like senses and the selection affect the buying behaviour of customers considering recent researches regarding similar concepts the study is further looked at in a detailed manner.

OBJECTIVES

- To measure the impact of sensory on demographic variables.
- To understand the impact of sensory on a selection of apparel.
- To analyse the impact of senses on buying behaviour of apparel.

HYPOTHESES

- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on demographic factors.
- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on age.
- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on gender.
- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on qualification.

There is no significant relationship between senses (visual, auditory and kinaesthetic) and selection behaviour of the consumer.

There is no significant relationship between the sensory appeals and buying behaviour of the consumer.

Sampling Plan: The data population included apparel consumers in engaged in browser mode shopping in speciality store format setting. The respondent data was collected using a structured questionnaire perceptions .The judgmental sampling method with inclusion parameters (age, location, gender and so on) was applied to the sample population.

Sample Size: Respondent data from 230 samples were collected belonging to varied demographics.

Sample Frame: the sample of respondents were drawn from the geographical area of Bangalore i.e., East, West, North, South and Central Zones, which included mall intercepts as a contact method.

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES OF DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Tools: The software used was SPSS Software and the tools used were: frequency distribution; Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin to test the sampling adequacy; Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity; Communality test to determine the correlation among the variables in a dataset; reliability to check the extent to which assessments are consistent; Chi-Square Test; correlation; and regression.

DATA ANALYSIS

The analyses is broadly classified into three approaches, namely:

- Frequency and descriptive statistics
- Test of the adequacy of the sample (KMO) and reliability tools
- Decision tools such as Chi-square, correlation, and regression.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Test Adequacy of Sample

Table-1: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.788
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4044.520
	d.f.	1225
	Sig.	.000

Sources: Authors Compilation

Normally, $0 < KMO < 1$

If $KMO > 0.5$, the sample is adequate.

Here, $KMO = 0.788$ which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed with the Factor Analysis.

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Taking a 95% level of Significance, $\alpha=0.05$

The p-value (Sig.) of $000 < 0.05$, therefore the Factor Analysis is valid.

As $p < \alpha$, therefore the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted indicating that there may be a statistically significant interrelationship between variables.

The Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test measure of sampling adequacy was used to examine the appropriateness of Factor Analysis. The approximate of Chi-Square is 4044.520 with 1225 degrees of freedom, which is significant at 0.05 Level of Significance. The KMO statistic of 0.788 is also large (greater than 0.50). Hence, Factor Analysis is considered as an appropriate technique for further Analysis of the data.

B. Reliability Statistics

Table-2: Reliability for the Different Dimensions

Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
1. Visual	.703	8
2. Auditory	.70	6
3. Kinaesthetic	.683	7
4. Design & Trend	.778	7
5. Price	.693	6
6. Impulse Buying	.683	6
7. Sales / Promotion / Advertisement	.693	6
8. Buying Behaviour	.725	4

Sources: Authors Compilation

Cronbach alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data. Most of the constructs are more than 0.6 and some are more than 0.7 which shows that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent responses to the items of the concerned constructs. An average of 0.707 is computed for a total of 50 items.

C. Chi-Square Analysis

1. Hypothesis Testing For Visual Sensory Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of customers.

Table-3: Chi-Square Tests: Visual Sensory Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Customers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	257.428 ^a	220	.042
Likelihood Ratio	172.239	220	.993
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.938	1	.005
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (257.428, $p=0.042$) is less than the table value (0.05) the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant relationship between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

2. Hypothesis Testing For Auditory Sensory Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between auditory sensory factors and the Buying behaviour of consumers.
 H₁: There is significant relationship between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-4: Chi-Square Tests: Auditory Sensory Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	157.868 ^a	140	.143
Likelihood Ratio	126.324	140	.790
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.513	1	.004
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (157.868, p=0.143) is more than the table value (0.05), the alternate hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant relationship between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is no inference between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

3. Hypothesis Testing For Kinaesthetic Sensory Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.
 H₁: There is a significant relationship between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-5: Chi-Square Tests: Kinaesthetic Sensory Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	184.376 ^a	150	.029
Likelihood Ratio	154.902	150	.375
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.285	1	.131
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (184.376, p=0.029) is less than the table value (0.05) so the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. There is significant relationship between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

4. Hypothesis Testing for Design and Trend Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between design and trend factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.
 H₁: There is a significant relationship between design and trend factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-6: Chi-Square Tests: Design and Trend Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	190.587 ^a	180	.280
Likelihood Ratio	158.756	180	.871
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.967	1	.026
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (190.587, p=0.280) is more than the table value (0.05) the alternate hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant relationship between design and trend factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is no inference between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

5. Hypothesis Testing for Price Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between price factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between price factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-7: Chi-Square Tests: Price Factors and Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	180.261 ^a	170	.280
Likelihood Ratio	148.023	170	.887
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001	1	.980
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (180.261, p=0.280) is more than the table value (0.05), the alternate hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant relationship between price factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is no inference between price factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

6. Hypothesis Testing for Impulse Buying Factors versus Buying Behaviour of the Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between impulse buying factors and the buying behaviour of consumers

H₁: There is significant relationship between impulse buying factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-8: Chi-Square Tests: Impulse Buying Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	270.762 ^a	150	.000
Likelihood Ratio	141.203	150	.684
Linear-by-Linear Association	29.214	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (270.762, p=0.000) is less than the table value (0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant relationship between impulse buying factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between impulse buying factors and the buying behaviour of customers.

7. Hypothesis Testing for Sales / Promotion / Advertisement Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between sales / promotion / advertisement factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

H₁: There is significant relationship between sales / promotion / advertisement factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-9: Chi-Square Tests: Sales / Promotion / Advertisement Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	318.482 ^a	200	.000
Likelihood Ratio	149.377	200	.997
Linear-by-Linear Association	25.661	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (318.482, p=0.000) is less than the table value (0.05) the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant relationship between sales / promotion / advertisement factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between sales / promotion / advertisement factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-10: Correlations

		Auditory	Kinaesthetic	Design & Trend	Price	Impulse Buying	Sales / Promo / Adv.	Buying Behaviour
Visual	Pearson Correlation	.475**	.278*	.489*	.347	.430**	.396**	.300**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.004
	N	232	232	232	232	232	232	89
Auditory	Pearson Correlation	.475**	.378**	.494**	.410**	.489	.495**	.311**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.003
	N	232	232	232	232	232	232	89
Kinaesthetic	Pearson Correlation	.278**	.378**	.429**	.158**	.360**	.264	.161**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.016	.000	.000	.131
	N	232	232	232	232	232	232	89
Design & Trend	Pearson Correlation	.489**	.494**	.429**	.438**	.409**	.446**	.238
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.025
	N	232	232	232	232	232	232	89
Price	Pearson Correlation	.347**	.410**	.158*	.438**	.312**	.307*	.003
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.087
	N	232	232	232	232	232	232	89
Impulse Buying	Pearson Correlation	.430**	.489**	.360**	.409**	.312**	.576**	.576**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	232	232	232	232	232	232	89
Sales / Promo / Advertisement	Pearson Correlation	.396**	.495**	.264**	.446**	.307**	.576**	.540**
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	232	232	232	232	232	232	89
Buying Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.300**	.311**	.161	.238*	.003	.576**	.540
	Sig (2-tailed)	.004	.003	.131	.025	.087	.000	.000
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	89

Sources: Authors Compilation

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

There is sum of each dimension to test for this study through the regression analysis method. It is assumed that the selection and buying of apparel are dependent on visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, price, impulse buying, sales / promotion / advertisement, design & trend and the overall buying behaviour. To test this hypothesis, multiple regression analysis was conducted with sum of visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, price, impulse buying, sales/ promotion / advertisement, design & trend (independent variables) and overall buying behaviour (dependent variable).

Table-11: Regression Analysis

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Visual		Enter
	Auditory		
	Kinesthetic		
	Design & Trend		
	Price		
	Impulse Buying		
	Sales / Promotion / Advertisement		

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Sum of acceptance

b. All requested variables entered.

Sources: Authors Compilation

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.641a	.411	.361	2.12017

Note: a. Predictors: (Constant), Sum_SPA, Kin_sum, Sum_Price, sum_visual, Auditory_sum, Sum_IB, Sum_DT

Sources: Authors Compilation

The adjusted R square value is 0.361. This means that the regression analysis can explain 36.1 % of the data and how close it is to the regression line. As such, visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, price, impulse buying, sales/ promotion/ advertisement, design & trend is highly dependent on the buying behaviour of customer.

Table-12: Anova Summary

Model	Sum of Squares	d.f.	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	254.459	7	36.351	8.087	.000b
Residual	364.103	81	4.495		
Total	618.562	88			

Note: a. Dependent Variable: buying behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Sum_SPA, Kin_sum, Sum_Price, sum_visual, Auditory_sum, Sum_IB, Sum_DT

Sources: Authors Compilation

In the analysis of variance table (ANOVA), the null hypothesis is tested, i.e. there is no impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables against the alternate hypothesis. In other words, the independent variables: visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, price, impulse buying, sales/ promotion/ advertisement and design and trend do not have an impact over the dependent variable, buying behaviour of the consumers. The p value from the ANOVA table is 0.000, which is less than the significance value of 0.05 and the null hypothesis is rejected. In other words, alternate hypothesis is accepted and it can be inferred that there exists a significant impact of visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, price, impulse buying, sales / promotion / advertisement, design & trend on the buying behaviour of the consumers.

FINDINGS

The Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test measure of sampling adequacy was used to examine the appropriateness of Factor Analysis. The approximate of Chi-Square is 4044.520 with 1225 degrees of freedom, which is significant at 0.05 Level of Significance. The KMO statistic of 0.788 is also large (greater than 0.50). Hence Factor Analysis is considered as an appropriate technique for further Analysis of the data.

Cronbach alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument, which is used to collect the data. Most of the constructs are more than 0.6 and some are more than 0.7, which shows that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent response to the items of the concerned constructs. An average of 0.707 is computed for a total of 50 items.

There is significant relationship between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

There is significant relationship between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

There is significant relationship between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

There is no significant relationship between design and trend factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

There is no significant relationship between price factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

There is significant relationship between impulse buying factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

There is significant relationship between sales/ promotion/ advertisement factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

The correlations of buying behaviour factors with all the seven analysed dimensions (i.e. visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, design & trend, impulse buying, sales / promotion / advertisement and price) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level).

It also shows that the null hypothesis is rejected for all the dimensions except the kinaesthetic and price factors and therefore there is significant relationship between buying behaviour factors and the other dimensions. Since the observed value for price factor v/s buying behaviour is $0.087 > 0.05$, the alternate hypothesis is rejected i.e. there is no significant relationship between price factors and buying behaviour. Similarly for kinaesthetic sensory factors $0.131 > 0.05$ It indicates that more and more of buying behaviour cues help in selection and other such factors. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between buying behaviour cue and dimensions such as visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, design & trend, impulse buying, sales/promotion/ advertisement and price is moderate.

Regression Inference: The adjusted R square value is 0.361. This means that the regression analysis can explain 36.1 % of the data and how close it is to the regression line. As such, visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, price, impulse buying, sales / promotion / advertisement, design and trend is highly dependent on the buying behaviour of customer

ANOVA Inference : The p value $0.000 < \text{significance value of } 0.05$ and thus we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which in this case is visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, price, impulse buying, sales / promotion / advertisement, design & trend and buying behaviour are dependent on each other

CONCLUSION

From the study it is evident that there is significant impact of the independent variables: visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, impulse buying and sale on the selection on the buying behaviour of the consumer. It also shows how a few factors do not affect the buying behaviour of consumers, that is, the dimensions such as price and design and trends.

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